

D8.2 LIFE PRISTINE website

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Project Acronym:	LIFE PRISTINE
Grant agreement no:	101074430
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Leader of this deliverable:	Iván García (EUT)
Contributors:	Lucía Arévalo (EUT)
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Deliverable Information Sheet

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0.3	23/01/2023	Ana Jiménez (ACC)	2 nd revision

Executive summary

This deliverable explains how LIFE PRISTINE project webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. This document summarizes the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project. Also, the data protection measures adopted within the site.

[NOTE: Front page and Executive summary will be published in the website for all deliverables]

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1 Overall principles

According to the work plan, EUT is responsible for designing and implementing the official PRISTINE project website. Following the recommendations of the European Commission, this page has been embedded in a specific URL registered in EUT's website: <https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine/>

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. **The website will be the anchor for all communication activities related to the project and serve as the main networking tool and a central point of entry for all public material**, including the project's basic information, expected impacts and objectives.

The website will be continuously updated with results, news, links to other relevant sites and projects, details of published papers, newsletters, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active during at least five years after the project's finalization.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project approved by partners, and it gives access to PRISTINE social media channels.

Considering that different authors might update the site, the Content Management System (CMS) adopted facilitates to easily and quickly publish the content.

Regarding the website language, all content will be available in English.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smartphones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

2 Website structure

The following information architecture for the LIFE PRISTINE website is proposed in the figure below. This website is a one-page type of website, meaning that the creation of subpages linked to different sections is not planned.

In turquoise you can see the sections that have been created for the website launch, while, in blue, the sections that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Figure 1. Website structure

3 Website content

In the following sections we describe the contents that have been published in the website launch.

3.1 Slider

The top of the page displays one slider: *“Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern in water treatment systems”*.

Figure 2. View of the main slider

PRISTINE in a nutshell

Removing Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams thanks to the PRISTINE Integrated Solution

3.2 About the project

LIFE PRISTINE project aims to develop the **PRISTINE Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams**. The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be adaptable on a case-by-case basis for **drinking water (DW)**, to protect humans from CECs, and for **wastewater (WW)**, to protect the environment and remove these contaminants from the water cycle.

LIFE PRISTINE will focus on perfluoroalkyl chemicals (PFAS), pesticides, pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCPs), toxins, antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) and microplastics as target contaminants, designated according previous studies in the two demo sites and existing literature.

LIFE PRISTINE goal is to **effectively remove >80% of every CECs in WW and DW scenarios**, going further if requested by existing legislation. Furthermore, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be cost-effective, 30% lower OpEx cost that comparable technologies.

Key Data

- **Start-end date:** 1 August 2022 - 31 July 2025
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Funder under:** LIFE Programme LIFE-2021-SAP-ENV
- **Overall budget:** 3,764,689.07€

- Reference number: 101074430 - LIFE21-ENV-ES-PRISTINE

A synergistic combination of individual technologies

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution is based on the integration of **encapsulated adsorbent technology, hollow-fibre nanofiltration (NF) membranes, and Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP) processes** (UV-LED combined with ozonation and/or H₂O₂), being these technologies controlled and optimised by a **Decision Support System** fed by Artificial Intelligence-based soft-sensors for the online estimation of CECs concentration levels.

In opposition to other existing technologies, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution will **permanently remove CECs from water**, thus directly applying **Zero Waste and Circular Economy principles** and coming ahead of existing and near future CECs regulations.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

LIFE PRISTINE project aims to develop the **PRISTINE Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams**. The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be adaptable on a case-by-case basis for **drinking water (DW)**, to protect humans from CECs, and for **wastewater (WW)**, to protect the environment and remove these contaminants from the water cycle.

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Figure 3. View of the About the project section

Which are the objectives?

1. To contribute to achieve a **CEC-free environment** by developing the PRISTINE Integrated Solution able to remove at least 80% CECs in wastewater (WW) and drinking water (DW) treatment systems.
2. To (long-term) **demonstrate the PRISTINE Integrated Solution in two relevant scenarios**, in a DW treatment plant and in a WW treatment plant, always guaranteeing in the later, a reduction under the levels required by Directive 2020/2184 /EC, and Directive 2013/39/EU, and also under PNEC levels in Watch Lists (Decision 2020/1161).
3. To ensure **market uptake of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution** by developing an appropriate strategy, aligning both business and governance interests and needs
4. To support **policy development, regulatory action, and risk communication towards Green Deal and Zero Pollution and Circular Economy Action Plans**

- To make sure that PRISTINE project results reach the necessary stakeholders from the industry, scientific community and society as a whole.

Which are the objectives?

LIFE PRISTINE main objective is to develop and demonstrate an **innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams**.

Thus, this main objective covers the **5 R's philosophy** of the project, as detailed in the following **specific objectives**, including those to ensure an efficient environment for communication, dissemination and replicability of results.

Figure 4. View of the objectives description

3.2.1 PRISTINE Integrated Solution

The Project intends to develop and demonstrate the **PRISTINE Integrated Solution**: a **versatile combination of adsorption, NF and AOPs** and that is able to remove CECs in a more sustainable and cost-effective way, by **permanently eliminating the compounds present in the water environment** instead of relocating them in other media, as current available technologies would do.

- Encapsulated adsorbents
- Hollow-fibre NF membranes
- Advanced Oxidation UV-LED reactor
- AI- based soft sensors

PRISTINE Integrated Solution

The Project intends to develop and demonstrate the **PRISTINE Integrated Solution**: a **versatile combination of adsorption, nanofiltration and advanced oxidation processes (AOP)** and that aims to remove CECs in a more sustainable and cost-effective way. Thereby CECs in the water environment shall not only be relocated into other media and waste streams, but the release of CECs to the water cycle shall be permanently reduced.

- ▶ Encapsulated adsorbents
- ▶ Hollow-fibre nanofiltration membranes
- ▶ Advanced Oxidation UV-LED reactor
- ▶ Artificial intelligence based soft sensors

Figure 5. View of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution section

3.2.2 The problem of CECs

The European Union defines the so-called **Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs)** as substances that have the potential to enter the environment and cause **adverse ecological and human health effects** but are still largely unregulated and whose fate and potential effects are poorly understood.

CECs can be **broadly classed into several categories** of chemicals such as pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCP), cyanotoxins, nanoparticles, illicit drugs, antibacterial, hormones, disinfection by-products (DBP), artificial sweeteners, benzotriazoles, 1,4-dioxane, perfluoroalkyl chemicals (PFA), microplastics, and antibiotic resistance genes (ARG), as well as emerging contaminants on the horizon such as prions and ionic liquids.

CECs present risks for human health such as immune system impairing or endocrine disrupting effects, carcinogenicity and/or mutagenicity, and are related to the infections caused by multi-drug resistant bacteria.

Understanding CECs' occurrence, mobility, degradation, toxicity (short-long term) and bioavailability it is still a challenge. It is needed to protect human health and environment, since **several contamination cases continue unknown due to the lack of detection techniques, regulatory policies, and impact assessments.**

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Figure 6. View of the CECs problem description

3.3 Demonstration scenarios

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be demonstrated in **operationally representative conditions for drinking water and wastewater treatment**, running for a year each.

The PRISTINE Integrated Pilot Plant constructed will be first installed and demonstrated at in a **Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP)** in Murcia.

After that testing, the demonstration plant will be sent to the drinking water treatment scenario in the **Bilbao Bizkaia Advanced Water Treatment Centre (CATABB)**, to be demonstrated for 12 additional months .

Both demo activities, to be carried out by ACCIONA, will count with the support of technology providers EUT, NXF and Xylem.

DEMONSTRATION SCENARIOS

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be demonstrated in operationally representative conditions for drinking water and wastewater treatment, running for a year each.

The PRISTINE Integrated Pilot Plant constructed will be installed at in a Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) in Murcia.

After that testing, the demonstration plant will be sent to the wastewater treatment scenario to be demonstrated for 12 additional months in the Bilbao Bizkaia Advanced Water Treatment Centre (CATABB), with the support of technology providers Eurecat, NX Filtration and Xylem.

Figure 7. View of the "Demonstration scenarios" section

3.4 Consortium

ACCIONA

ACCIONA leads the water treatment sector through the design, construction and operation of reverse osmosis desalination infrastructures, drinking water treatment plants (DWTPs), wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and tertiary treatments for water reuse, with a recently reinforced focus on services for cities.

Figure 8. ACCIONA logo

The total population that benefits from ACCIONA water services is about 100 million people in 30 countries of the 5 continents. In 2021, the company treated almost 1,033 hm³ of water, 50.4 % in water stress areas. Innovation plays a key strategic role in ACCIONA daily business activities, revealed by the many technological innovations included in WTPs and WWTPs built/operated by ACCIONA and developed by ACCIONA's Innovation Department.

Contribution to LIFE PRISTINE

ACCIONA is the LIFE PRISTINE project coordinator. Besides the management role, ACCIONA leads the development of the CECs AI-based soft sensor and of the LIFE PRISTINE Integrated Solution for CECs removal in drinking and wastewater streams, integrating digital mathematical models which replicate physical individual processes part of the solution. This versatile Integrated Solution will be governed by a Decision Support System implementing AI techniques whose development will fall under ACCIONA's responsibility. In addition,

assessment, transferability and replication actions will be coordinated by ACCIONA, with the support of the rest of the partners.

Twitter: www.twitter.com/ACCIONA

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/showcase/acciona_agua/

Eurecat

[Eurecat](#) is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

Figure 9. Eurecat logo

The centre offers to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat

is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to LIFE PRISTINE

Eurecat is responsible, through its Chemical Technology Unit, of the development of an adsorption capsule system for CECs elimination, both in drinking water and in wastewater scenarios. Moreover, it is in charge of running the different communication and dissemination activities of the project, designed to maximise its visibility and to reach the identified stakeholders.

Twitter: [@Eurecat_News](https://twitter.com/Eurecat_News)

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ___t_6ozc7bDaKZw

NX FILTRATION

Figure 10. NX Filtration logo

[NX Filtration](#) is a leading manufacturer for advanced hollow fiber membranes for nanofiltration, ultrafiltration and microfiltration applications. NX Filtration's membrane technology is capable of selectively removing organics from polluted water, including micropollutants, color, antibiotics, PFAS, bacteria and viruses.

This has resulted in new and simple processes for the treatment of water, the reuse of wastewater and the production of potable water. We deliver robust products and innovative solutions enabling our partners to excel in sustainable membrane filtration applications.

Contribution to LIFE PRISTINE

NX Filtration will provide advanced hollow fibers direct nanofiltration membranes for pilot trials execution on drinking water and wastewater facilities, which has been demonstrated for successful elimination of certain types of persistent mobile compounds (including PFAS and pesticides), and identify PMC rejection performance of different membrane types and processing conditions allowing the technology to either be modified during operation or to be optimally implemented on sites based on the PMC type and concentration.

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nx-filtration/>

ESAMUR

Figure 11. ESAMUR logo

ESAMUR is a public company created by the Law 3/2000, of July 12, of Sewerage and Wastewater Treatment and Implantation of the Sewerage fee in Murcia Region. The Law of Sewerage assigns to ESAMUR the task of collecting and managing the Sewerage fee, applying these economic resources to the tasks of exploitation, maintenance and control of the public facilities of wastewater treatment in Murcia Region (Spain).

Contribution to LIFE PRISTINE

ESAMUR, as manager of the Ceutí WWTP, will coordinate the analytical campaign for the characterization of waste water, moreover will contribute its experience and support to the demonstration activities, the evaluation of the impact of the project, the development of actions related to policies and support the activities of communication and dissemination.

Twitter: https://twitter.com/esamur_aguas?lang=es

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/esamuraguas/?hl=es>

Facebook: <https://es-la.facebook.com/esamuraguas/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/esamuraguas/?originalSubdomain=es>

XYLEM

Figure 12. Xylem logo

Xylem is a leading water technology company committed to “solving water” by creating innovative and smart technology solutions to meet the world’s water, wastewater and energy needs.

In a world of ever-growing challenges, Xylem delivers innovative water technology solutions throughout the cycle of water.

Our technological strength across the life cycle of water is second-to-none. From collection and distribution to reuse and return to nature, our highly efficient water technologies, industrial pumps and application solutions not only use less energy and reduce life-cycle costs, but also promote sustainability.

Contribution to LIFE PRISTINE

Xylem is the technology provider and developer, contributing with their expertise in Oxidation (Ozone), Disinfection (UV) and Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP), that capitalizes on their 40 years of experience and more than two hundred fifty thousand water and wastewater treatment installations worldwide.

The innovation, development and integration of new UV-LED technology for treatment processes and reactor designs through the deep involvement of their Research and Development team (R&D) will bring the UV-LED technology forward. This progress is needed to bring UV-LED technology nearer to a new standard for water purification challenges and for combating emerging contaminants in water streams.

LinkedIn: <http://www.linkedin.com/company/xylem-inc->

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/Xylem>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/xylemincorporated>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/xylem_inc/

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/user/XylemIncorporated>

CONSORTIUM

- > ACCIONA
- > Eurecat
- > NX Filtration
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@ACCIONA

ACCIONA Agua

Figure 13. View of the "Consortium" section

3.5 News & events

This section shows articles on LIFE PRISTINE project advances and results, as well as information related to project meetings or articles written by partners on project topics.

It will also include an agenda announcing events where LIFE PRISTINE consortium is organising or attending/participating (conferences, meetings, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

Within this page project events such as the final conference, webinars and workshops will be announced and promoted. Each event will count with a specific page with the information on the event, agenda and form to register. After the event, the presentations and documents delivered during the event will be made available for download through the page, as well as video recording of the sessions.

NEWS & EVENTS

<p>17 11, 2022</p>	<p>Acciona presents the LIFE PRISTINE project at the 3rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals novembre 17th, 2022</p> <p>Maria del Mar Micó, partner from project coordinator ACCIONA, has presented the LIFE PRISTINE project during the 3rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals (YWP) 2022, celebrated on November 16th-19th at the School of Engineering of the University of Valencia (ETSE-UV), Spain. During her presentation, entitled "Emerging pollutants in [...]"</p>	
<p>21 09, 2022</p>	<p>Acciona leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in the end-to-end water cycle setembre 21st, 2022</p> <p>The LIFE PRISTINE project combines water treatment processes with artificial intelligence-based digital tools to develop a solution that removes emerging pollutants in the integrated water cycle. The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in a representative full-scale operational environment. LIFE PRISTINE, with a budget of 4 million [...]</p>	

Figure 14. View of the "News & Events" section

3.6 Resources

This page will gather all public materials of the project, including visual materials, videos, public deliverables, scientific publications, and media features. Specific sections for each type of content.

Main outcomes:

- **Deliverables:** all public reports will be published on this website for in-depth access to project outputs.
- **Promotional materials:** project promotional materials produced (rollups, info sheets, posters, etc).
- **Scientific publications:** all scientific articles related to the project's research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.
- **Audio-visual materials:** a set of short videos will be produced to present LIFE PRISTINE's concept and impacts.
- **Media impacts:** main articles featuring LIFE PRISTINE project in generalist and specialised media outlets.
- **Newsletters:** the four newsletters (one by each year) produced within the course of the project will be available.

3.7 Networking

This section will include a description of different projects related to LIFE PRISTINE, as well as a list of joint initiatives carried out.

3.8 Interested?

This section includes a button leading to the signup form for the [PRISTINE Community of Interest](#). The audience subscribing to the mailing list will receive the annual newsletter of the project.

Besides, direct access to the project’s Twitter and LinkedIn channels is provided through buttons.

Figure 15. View of the “Interested?” section

4 Layout

The LIFE PRISTINE website is a single page without own menu, meaning that all information is found by scrolling through it. However, the different articles produced to inform about the activities of the project will be published in a specific page for each post. In the main website, the title of the article and the main picture will be shown.

The header and footer show EUT information, as LIFE PRISTINE page is embedded in the technology center’s website.

A specific footer has been created to acknowledge the funding of the project. It shows the following text, together with the European and the LIFE Programme flags:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Figure 16. View of the footer

5 Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by EUT with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The LIFE PRISTINE website will be updated with new content and information every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved or there is other news worth publishing.

6 Analytics

The LIFE PRISTINE website uses Google Analytics and Matomo to monitor all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. On the near future, transition from Google Analytics to Google Analytics 4 (GA4) will take place.

7 Site hosting, installation and maintenance

EUT has been responsible for setting up the website (hosting and configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

On the other hand, EUT is the partner responsible for maintaining the site, adding content and updating it regularly. The page has been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that LIFE PRISTINE website is well positioned in the browsers. The website will be maintained for at least five years after the projects' end.

8 Data protection

LIFE PRISTINE website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR.

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements.

The latest version of the AEPD "Guidelines on the Use of Cookies", compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click "I accept". In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website <https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine>, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

The users may revise their cookies' selection at any time as the Cookies Setting Banner is available at the bottom right part of the page. The website also includes specific pages for allocating the privacy policy (<https://eurecat.org/en/privacy-policy/>), the cookies policy (<http://eurecat.org/en/politica-de-cookies/>) and the legal disclaimer (<https://eurecat.org/en/disclaimer/>).

The webpage includes two forms gathering personal data from users: a contact form to manage user's queries and an external sign-up form for users to subscribe to LIFE PRISTINE's Community of Interest. For both forms EUT is the data controller. The data of the contact form will be transferred to partners involved in the project to better reply to the requests, while the users' data of the community of interest will not be disclosed to third-parties, and will be processed by Mailchimp.

The website will also include specific forms to manage the registration of interest users to project events. The data included in these forms will be disclosed with the organising partner with the solely objective to register the users to the event and be able, afterwards, to send event materials to attendees.

8.1 Disclaimer

By fulfilling Spanish Information Society Services and Electronic Commerce Act 34 of 11 July 2002, Users are hereby informed that the owner of the website www.eurecat.org is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, the identification details of which are as follows:

Registered office: Avda. Universidad Autònoma, 23
Postcode: 08290 Town: Cerdanyola del Vallès Province: Barcelona
Tax Identification Code (CIF): G66210345
Email address: legal@eurecat.org
Registry details: Recorded in the Foundations Registry of the Autonomous Government of Catalonia with number 2826.

1. Accessing the website:

This Disclaimer regulates Users' access and use of the website in order to provide information about the institution's services and products and allow all Internet Users general access thereto.

The persons accessing and/or using the website are considered to hold the position of Users and implies their acceptance, with no reservations of any kind, of each and all of these general terms and conditions, as well as other special terms and conditions, if any, which govern the use of the Portal and the services associated therewith.

Users must carefully read the Disclaimer and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right, at any time and with no prior notice being necessary, to carry out any modification or update of the contents and services, these access and use provisions and, in general terms, any element included in the website's design and configuration. If Users do not accept the conditions for access and use, they must abstain from using the website and its contents.

2. Using the Website:

Users must carefully use the website, as well as the information related to the services and/or activities offered there, being fully subject to the applicable regulations as well as the rules for moral and generally accepted good conduct and public order, as well as the conditions for access and use and any other terms and conditions included on the website.

Moreover, Users must refrain from using any of the contents for illegal purposes or objectives that are prohibited by virtue this document and that could harm the rights and interests of third parties, or could damage, disable, overload, harm or hinder the normal use of the website's contents, other Users or any other Internet User (hardware and software).

3. Functioning of the Website:

If the User fails to comply with the terms and conditions in this Disclaimer or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to restrict, suspend and/or refuse access to the website, adopting any technical measures that may be necessary for such purpose. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will make every possible effort to maintain the correct functioning of the website, avoiding any errors or repairing them, and to keep the contents up-to-date. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability or continuity of access to the website nor the absence of errors in the contents thereof.

4. Liability:

Users are the sole parties responsible for the use they could make of any of the website's information or mechanisms.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT shall not be held liable for any damage to Users' hardware and/or software caused by accessing or using the website. Similarly, it shall not be held liable for the damages that could be caused due to accessing and/or using the information on the website and, in particular, those that may occur in IT systems or caused by a virus and/or cyber-attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defect in communication systems and/or the Internet.

Users shall be held liable for any damages that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT could be caused as a result of failing to comply with any of the obligations undertaken by virtue of this Disclaimer, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

5. Policy on links (linking website and linked website):

1. a) Linking website:

Third parties that intend to include a link to this website on a different website must fulfil the laws in force and may not host inappropriate, illegal, pornographic or violent content, etc.

Under no circumstances whatsoever shall FUNDACIÓ EURECAT be held liable for the contents of the website nor does it promote, guarantee, monitor or recommend the contents thereof. If the linking Website does not comply with any of the aforementioned terms and conditions, it must delete the link immediately.

1. b) Linked website:

This website may include links to websites belonging to third parties that Users are allowed to access. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT shall not be held responsible for the contents of these linked websites, instead Users will be responsible for accepting and checking the link every time they access it.

The purpose of these links or notifications does not imply the support, approval, marketing or any relationship whatsoever between Fundació Eurecat and the persons or institutions that own the sites where they are located.

6. Intellectual and industrial property rights for the contents:

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or its licensors are the holders of all the intellectual property rights regarding the contents of the website, this being deemed to mean all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (including source codes), as well as the different elements included on the website (texts, images, photos, colours, etc.), structure, order, etc. The

trademarks and trade names (“distinctive signs”) are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the website by Users does not imply the assignment of any intellectual or industrial property right thereto. The User is categorically prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, providing or, in any other manner, publicly disclosing, converting or modifying the contents or the distinctive signs, unless it has obtained authorisation from the holder of the corresponding rights, or if it is legally allowed.

7. Advertising:

The website may host advertising or sponsored contents. The advertisers or sponsors are solely responsible for ensuring that the material submitted to be included on the website fulfils the laws that may be applicable in each case.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT shall not be held liable for any error, inaccuracy or irregularity that the advertising and sponsored contents may contain.

8. Applicable law:

This Disclaimer shall be governed and construed according to Spanish law.

The parties hereby agree to submit any dispute that may arise related to access to the website to the jurisdiction of the relevant courts and tribunals, according to consumer and user regulations.

9. Contact:

Users may contact us through this email address: legal@eurecat.org for any query or comment regarding this disclaimer.

8.2 Privacy policy

Who is the controller of your personal data?

Data Controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax Identification Code (CIF): G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone number: +34 93 238 14 00

The Data Protection Officer’s email address: dpo@eurecat.org

Why do we process your personal data?

The data provided in the contact form will solely and exclusively be used to answer the Users’ queries and to keep them up to date on the news and services provided by EURECAT, if they grant their express authorisation for the latter purpose.

There could be forms on our website that collect users’ data for specific purposes. In these cases, this will be subject to the specific terms and conditions in each case.

Is it compulsory to provide all the information requested in the forms on the website?

Regarding the form on the website, Users must complete the spaces marked “compulsory”. If they do not complete the required personal data or only partially provide them this could mean that Fundación Eurecat is unable to deal with their requests and therefore Fundación Eurecat will be exonerated from all liability for not rendering or not fully rendering the requested services.

The personal data that Users provide to Fundación Eurecat must be current data so that the information in our records is up-to-date and error-free. Users will be held liable for the data provided being true.

How long will we keep your personal data?

The personal data will be kept while the reason lasts for which they were provided and their deletion or cancelation has not been requested.

What is the legal basis for processing users’ personal data?

The legal basis for processing personal data is the consent granted by accepting the personal data processing clause.

To whom will users’ data be disclosed?

Data will not be disclosed to third companies, unless there is a legal obligation to do so. If there is any intention to disclose them, the authorisation of the data subjects will be obtained beforehand.

What are users’ rights regarding their personal data?

Users may exercise their right of access to their personal data and to request rectification of any incorrect data or, if need be, request deletion when the data are no longer necessary for the purposes for which they were obtained. They may also request restriction, portability and objection to their data being processed under certain circumstances and for reasons related to their particular situation.

They are also entitled to withdraw their consent at any time without this retroactively affecting the personal data processing carried out up to such time.

Users may exercise their aforementioned rights, according to the terms and conditions in the law in force, at the registered office of EURECAT or by submitting a request by email to legal@eurecat.org.

If they do not obtain a satisfactory reply and wish to file a claim or obtain further information about any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es) - C/ Jorge Juan, 6 in Madrid, Spain).

Which security measures has the company implemented?

Fundación Eurecat hereby informs users that it has implemented the required technical and organisational security measures to ensure the security of users’ personal data and prevent their alteration, loss, unauthorised processing and/or access according to the state of the art, the nature of the data stored and the risks to which they are exposed, whether due to a human action or physical or natural media, according to the provisions in the regulations in force.

Social media

Fundación Eurecat has profiles on different social media websites in order to advertise and publish information about the services it renders through its website, to interact with the users and to use these networks as a channel for social encounters and interaction.

We provide links below to the privacy policies of the social media websites where Fundació Eurecat has an active profile:

- Facebook: <https://ca-es.facebook.com/privacy/explanation>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/es/privacy>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/intl/es/yt/about/policies/#community-guidelines>
- LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/legal/privacy-policy?_l=es_ES

8.3 Cookies

What are cookies and what are they used for?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. Some of the cookies used on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

What kind of cookies exist?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.

- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

What kind of cookies does the website use?

The user may be consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, this cookie does not require the user's agreed neither its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
_ga	0	2 years	This cookie is installed by Google Analytics. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, campaign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies store information anonymously and assigns a randomly generated number to identify unique visitors.
APISID	Third Party	2 years	This cookie is used by Google to display personalized advertisements on Google sites, based on recent searches and previous interactions. AID, TAID. These cookies link your activities to other devices on which you previously logged in via your Google-account.
cli_user_preference	0	1 year	This cookie stores consolidated information of consent of all categories in the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. This cookie is used to ensure the smooth functioning of the plugin with certain cache plugins.
CONSENT	Third Party	2 years	This cookie carries out information about how the end user uses the website and any advertising that the end user may have seen before visiting the said website.
cookieinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary".
cookieinfo-checkbox-non-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Non Necessary".

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
CookieLawInfoConsent	0	1 year	The cookie is used to store the summary of the consent given for cookie usage. It does not store any personal data
HSID	Third Party	2 years	This cookie is defined by DoubleClick (owned by Google) to create a profile of the website visitor's interests and to display relevant ads on other sites.
LOGIN_INFO	Third Party	2 years	This cookie is used to play YouTube videos embedded on the website.
PHPSESSID	Session	Session	The PHPSESSID cookie is native to PHP and enables websites to store serialized state data. On the Action website, it is used to establish a user session and to pass state data via a temporary cookie, which is commonly referred to as a session cookie. As the PHPSESSID cookie has no timed expiry, it disappears when the client is closed.
PREF	Third Party	2 years	This cookie, which may be set by Google or Doubleclick, may be used by advertising partners to build a profile of interests to show relevant ads on other sites. It works by uniquely identifying your browser and device.
SAPISID	Third Party	2 years	This cookie enable Google to collect user information for videos hosted by YouTube.
SID	Third Party	2 years	Google uses this cookie to identify users sessions and show them ads.
SIDCC	Third Party	2 years	This cookie carries out information about how the end user uses the website and any advertising that the end user may have seen before visiting the said website.
SSID	Third Party	2 years	This cookie carries out information about how the end user uses the website and any advertising that the end user may have seen before visiting the said website.
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
VISITOR_INFO1_LIVE	Third Party	2 years	This cookie is set by Youtube to keep track of user preferences for Youtube videos embedded in sites; it can also determine whether the website visitor is using the new or old version of the Youtube interface.
YSC	0	Session	This cookie is set by YouTube to track views of embedded videos.

How do you disable cookies in a browser?

The cookies set up is directly reflected to the browser used, however here are additional information about how the user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered as a Third-party cookies. For example, in case of user chooses Google’s browser and uses its translate tool of the full website, Google install its own cookies in the user’s computers which are not managed by the website publisher as well as has not liability about them. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#).
- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#).

Further informartion

Further information about cookies as well as how to block them at www.allaboutcookies.org, www.youronlinechoices.eu. For any questions or comments about this website cookies, shall contact by email to info@eurecat.org as a web publisher or as a web service supplier.

8.4 Community of interest data treatment information

Data Controller: The Data Controller is Fundació Eurecat, with Vat number G66210345 sited at Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290, Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN), legal@eurecat.org (the “Data Controller”).

Data Protection Officer contact information de contact dpo@eurecat.org

Purposes of the data treatment: identifying data (name, surname, email address) and professional data (business activity, position) shall be processed to submitting you information related the checkbox selected which are Live Praline's and Eurecat's projects, as well as to profiling you to segment the newsletter activity to your interests.

Legal Basis: the legal basis for processing your data is the consent granted (GDPR art 6.1 a).

Recipients: The data shall not be ceded to third parties; however, the data may be accessible to third parties as to the Data Controller services providers or, because of legal obligations. Further information at [Privacy Policy](#).

Storage: The data shall be stored for the term required to develop the purpose of the treatment, or, until the data subject request its deletion.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data shall not be object to automated decisions. The data from the form shall be used to segment each information shipment to those subject matters that according to your profile may interest you. Further information at [Privacy Policy](#).

Rights: the consent may be revoked at any time. You may also have the right to access, rectify, erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing data and to ask for the portability of the data according to the legal conditions contacting the Data Controller at: **Fundació Eurecat** a Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), or, by email a legal@eurecat.org

Supervisory Authority: in case the user shall not obtained the execution of a right petition, or its the response or, shall be considered it unsatisfactory, or require further information about the subject's data rights, you may consult to the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.agpd.es).

Further Information: you may consult further information about the data treatment at [Privacy Policy](#)